

FORMATION OF COPPER AND COPPER SILICIDE THIN FILMS USING MAGNETRON SPUTTERING

¹K.Dovranov, ²M. Normuradov, ³I.Bekpulatov, ⁴V. Loboda, ⁵Kh.Davranov, ⁶M.Davlatov,
⁷A.Kodirov, ⁸M.Vinnichenko, ⁹Kh.Turakulov

^{12,3,5,6,7,8,9}Karshi State University, Karshi, Uzbekistan, 180119

⁴Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Saint Petersburg, Russian Federation

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We report on the formation of copper silicide nanofilms using different modes of magnetron sputtering [8]. The thickness of the resulting heteroepitaxial Cu/Cu₁₅Si₄/Si film was measured using SEM. Also, a Cu₁₅Si₄ film was formed by thermally heating Cu/Si(111) nanofilms in vacuum at 800 K for 1.5 h using the DCMS method. The thickness and surface morphology of the obtained samples were studied using SEM. The formation of silicide films is confirmed by the results of energy dispersive spectra. The formation of the copper silicide film depends on the copper crystal size and the substrate temperature, and at 470°C, a 75 nm thick Cu₁₅Si₄ film was formed under a 130 nm thick copper layer. The formation of copper and its silicide films during magnetron sputtering was found to depend on the substrate temperature and the post-heating temperature.

Detailed information on the mechanism of formation of thin copper films in different operating modes of the magnetron sputtering device on the surface of single-crystal silicon by the solid-phase ion-plasma method is presented. The dependence of the sputtering rate of Cu/Si(111) films obtained by the methods of direct current magnetron sputtering and high-frequency magnetron sputtering on the sputtering time and the distance between the target and the substrate is studied. The surface morphology and electrophysical properties of Cu/Si(111) thin films are analyzed.

Figure 1. Dependence of the deposition rate of a copper target, obtained by different methods, on the distance from the base to the target.

The maximum sputtering rate of $\approx 11 \text{ \AA/s}$ was achieved at the optimal distance between the base and the target of 90 mm (Fig.1).

According to the results of the study, it was found that the formation of Cu and its silicide nanofilms from a copper target using the DCMS and RFMS methods of the magnetron device depends on the initial temperature of the substrate or the subsequent heating temperatures of the film. The optimal temperature for crystallization of the films was found to be 470°C. The surface morphology of the formed copper silicide nanofilms was measured and analyzed using an atomic force microscope and an Olympus “LEXT™ OLS5100” laser confocal microscope (Figure 2).

Thanks to the advanced optical components, high-quality 3D measurements were obtained in these microscopes, and the surface roughness was found to be 6 nm.

Figure 2. Surface morphology of $\text{Cu}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ thin film formed by DCMS method.
 a) Surface roughness image, b) 2D image, 3D image

Figure 3. Phase diagram of the Cu-Si system [9]

As a result of heating, the ϵ -phase of copper silicide has a very narrow concentration range of 21.05-21.13% (at.) Si, the ϵ -phase of $\text{Cu}_{15}\text{Si}_4$ remains stable at temperatures from 470 °C to 620 °C and below 570 °C, the γ -phase of $\text{Cu}_{56}\text{Si}_{11}$ is stable from the formation temperature of 729 °C to room temperature (Fig.3). This study advances scientific research in the field of copper silicide phase formation. The scientific significance of the research results lies in the fact that the mechanism of formation of thin films of copper (Cu) and its silicides on the surface of Si and dielectric substrates using direct current (DC) and radio frequency (RF) sputtering modes of a magnetron sputtering device has been established, the effect of sputtering time, sputtering power and subsequent thermal heating on the electrical conductivity of the film has been determined, and photoelectric and thermoelectric properties have been clarified. The practical significance of the research results is that thin films of Cu, $\text{Cu}_{15}\text{Si}_4$, formed on the surface of single-crystal silicon by the ion-plasma method using the DC and RF modes of a magnetron sputtering device, are widely used in chemical energy sources and as catalysts for various processes [9]. This study complements the knowledge on the use of copper-silicon alloys to improve the performance of metal-oxide-semiconductor transistors and high-speed integrated circuits (ICs).

